
Along Came Henry: A Guide Dog Story

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Juvenile fiction, soft cover

MaryBeth Gundrum and Bev Larsson. (2012). Underwood, QLD:
Inhouse Publishing. Illustrated by Annette Lodge

This delightful book is a love story that explores the unique relationship between a woman who is blind and her guide dog. The reader is first introduced to Bev, whose blindness limits her appreciation and connectedness with the world around her. The reader is then introduced to Henry, a rollicking, frolicking, mischievous puppy that undertakes guide dog training and is eventually assigned to Bev as a “working dog”. From here, the love story begins. With Henry at her side, Bev bursts out into the world around her with confidence and a spirit of adventure.

Bev Larsson and MaryBeth Gundrum have created a story that will resonate with all readers who know the joy of owing a dog. Child and adult readers alike will appreciate the simplicity and melodic nature of the rhyming prose and the beautiful watercolour illustrations that brim with life and capture Bev’s changing moods.

Importantly, this story book could have many uses. It could inform a young audience on a topic about which they would have no prior knowledge. Further, the book could be useful in preschool, kindergarten, or during the early primary school years to educate young children about the existence of vision impairment, with positive imagery and messages around disability and accessibility. These are important messages, particularly in mainstream educational environments where students with and without disability study together.

At the time of writing, Bev Larsson lived in Northern New South Wales, Australia with her guide dog Henry. Her co-author MaryBeth Gundrum was a Brisbane-based public relations and communications consultant in Australia. The book’s illustrator, Annette Lodge was a Sydney-based painter, author and illustrator of children’s books. The book is available for purchase from InHouse Publishing www.inhousebookstore.com.au

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